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RFID BASED SECURITY SYSTEM FOR MARKING ATTENDANCE WITH CAMERA OPTION

Porusu Ramanaiah

M.Tech. Scholar, Department of Computer Science and
Technology, Dhauj, Faridabad, Haryana, India

Rupak Kumar

Asst.Prof.Department of Computer Science
AL-Falah University, Faridabad, Haryana, India

Abstract:

Biometrics manages computerized strategy for recognizing a man or checking the personality of a man in light of the physiological or way of acting, as is utilized for verification in a significant number of the exchanges which has been done on the web. The biometric for security that has been chosen for implementation is fingerprint, since fingerprint biometric is easily available and highly reliable compared to many other biometrics. In the existing biometric authentication system the fingerprint template of a person is stored as such in the authentication server, person having age of 60 or more, matching of finger print is quite problematic, so we have suggested a solution in which if the fingerprint doesn't match our application prompted for otp, if the otp get matched our camera captured the image of a person and send it to authorized person via mail for authentication that who has entered the otp. If the otp doesn't get matched an alarm is being triggered.

Keywords- Fingerprint, Biometric, otp, rfid, webcam, SMTP, pc based

I. INTRODUCTION

Prints on finger are fully formed at about seven months of fetus development. General qualities of the unique mark develop as the skin on the fingertip starts to separate stream of amniotic liquids around the baby and its position in the uterus change amid the separation procedure. Hence the cells on the fingertip develop in a microenvironment that is marginally not the same as hand to hand and finger to finger.

Unique finger impression is an example of edges, wrinkles and details, which are separated utilizing inked impact on a paper or sensors.

Figure 1: Different fingerprint Images

Fingerprint have a center around which designs like twirls, circles, or curves are bended to guarantee that each print is remarkable like curve ,circle ,whorl

Figure 2. Examples of fingerprint classes

The edges and wrinkles are portrayed by inconsistencies known as particulars, the unmistakable element whereupon finger examining innovations are based. Particulars focuses are neighborhood edge qualities that happen at either an edge bifurcation or an edge finishing. The edge finishing is the time when an edge ends. Bifurcations are focuses at which a solitary edge parts into two edges. What’s more, designs are imperative in the investigation of fingerprints since no two fingers have been appeared as indistinguishable.

Figure 3 Minutiae points on fingerprint

Figure 4 Different types of minutiae

II. FINGERPRINT MATCHING TECHNIQUES

Unique mark MATCHING TECHNIQUES The huge number of ways to deal with unique finger impression coordinating can be coarsely characterized into three

1. **Correlation-based matching:** Two unique finger impression pictures are superimposed and the connection between comparing pixels is figured for various arrangements.
2. **Minutiae-based matching:** This is the most prominent and generally utilized strategy, being the premise of the unique finger impression correlation made by unique finger impression analysts. Minutiae are extricated from the two fingerprints and put away as sets of focuses in the two-dimensional plane. Particulars based coordinating basically comprises of finding the arrangement between the format and the info details sets that outcomes in the greatest number of particulars pairings.
3. **Pattern-based (or image-based) matching:** Pattern based algorithms think about the essential unique finger impression designs (curve, whorl, and circle) between a formerly put away format and a competitor unique finger impression. This requires the pictures be adjusted in a similar introduction. To do this, the calculation finds a main issue in the unique finger impression picture and focuses on that. The layout contains the sort, size, and introduction of examples inside the adjusted unique mark picture. The hopeful unique finger impression picture is graphically contrasted with the format with decide how much they coordinate. In Our venture we have actualized a details based coordinating procedure.

In Our project we have implemented a minutiae based matching technique. This approach has been seriously contemplated, likewise is the foundation of the current accessible unique mark acknowledgment items.

III. RELATED WORK

In our proposed solutions, we have trying to rectify the problem of authentication problem faced due to finger print matching. In previous research we have found that persons having age of more than 60 or above, lines or patterns of finger get distorted which create problem in matching of finger prints. In our proposed method we are using finger print image reader R305 KG167, webcam, and any windows operating system pc for transmission of image. Once the user place the finger on finger print reader module, we will store the finger print image in reader. We are using reader R305 KG167 for storing & matching of fingerprints. After non-matching of finger print our hardware popup for otp which it generates and sends it to registered number. Once the otp has been verified webcam capture the image of person who is entering the otp. If the otp didn't match arduino raise the alarm.

Figure 5: Fingerprint Authentication System

IV. PROBLEM FORMULATION: NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF PROPOSED RESEARCH

- Before the matching process can be done, the fingerprint must go through the identification part which is extraction of the fingerprint itself.
- Unique mark coordinating procedures can be put into two classes, particulars based and relationship based yet utilizing connection based the little relationships are frequently deciphered as noteworthy. A point design coordinating issue. A combinatorial issue requiring calculation outline instead of measurable example Recognition A point pattern matching problem.
- A combinatorial problem requiring algorithm design rather than statistical pattern Recognition solutions. The following are the challenges faced when matching minutiae point sets
- There is no inherent ordering in the collection of points.
- The point set is of variable size and does not fall into the traditional scheme of pattern recognition where the data is assumed to be represented as multi-variant vector instances.
- Furthermore the lack of knowledge about the point correspondences between the two points sets, make it a combinatorial problem requiring algorithm design rather than statistical pattern recognition solutions.
- Missing and occluded features are common and further complicate the process of matching.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

We have concentrated our implementation on Minutiae based method. In particular we are interested only in two of the most important minutia features i.e. Ridge Ending and Ridge bifurcation. (Figure 6)

Terminations Bifurcations

Figure 6(a) Ridge Ending, (b) Ridge Bifurcation

The outline of our approach can be broadly classified into 2 stages - Minutiae Extraction and Minutiae matching. Figure 6 illustrates the flow diagram of the same.

Figure 6: System Flow Diagram

The framework takes in 2 input fingerprints to be coordinated and gives a rate score of the degree of match between the two. In view of the score and limit coordinate esteem it can recognize whether the two fingerprints match or not. The info fingerprints are taken from the database given by FVC2004 (Fingerprint Verification Competition) as shown in Figure 7

Figure7: Implementation Procedure

Minutiae extraction incorporates Image Enhancement, Image Segmentation and Final Extraction forms while Minutiae coordinating incorporate Minutiae Alignment and Match

forms.

Figure 8: Detailed Design Description

- Under image enhancement step Histogram Equalization, Fast Fourier Transformation increases the quality of the image taken and Image Binarization converts the grey scale image to a binary image.
- After matching of finger print our hardware prompted for otp, if the otp get matched, camera captures the image of person who is sitting near it and mail it via smtp to the authorized person. If the otp didn't get matched alarm has been raised.

VI.DISCUSSION

The pursuits of knowledge on the diverse area of FPbiometric systems envisage the importance of FP biometric system to provide strong authentication. The summary of our study shows that of the FR is having edge over other biometric traits. Table I depicts performance comparison of different biometric technique based on parameters like EER, FAR and FRR. The enumerated review plays a pivotal role for establishing identity for the industry like law enforcement, forensic science community and with general public. This leads to the invention of next generation faster and higher quality acquisition devices.

Table I. Performance Comparison Of Biometric TechnologiesBased On Eer(Equal Error Rate), Far(False Acceptance Rate),Frr(False Rejection Rate)

Biometric	EER	FAR	FRR	Subjects	Comments
Face	NA	1%	10%	37437	varied light, indoor/outdoor
Finger print	2%	2%	2%	25000	rotation and exaggerated skin distortion
Hand geometry	1%	2%	2%	129	with rings and improper placement
Iris	0.01%	0.94%	0.99%	1224	indoor environment
Key strokes	1.8%	7%	0.1%	15	during 6 months period
voice	6%	2%	10%	30	text dependent and multilingual

VII.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The above usage was a push to see how Fingerprint Recognition is utilized as a type of biometric to perceive personalities of individuals. It incorporates every one of the phases from details extraction from fingerprints to particulars coordinating which produces a match score. Different standard strategies are utilized as a part of the middle of the road phases of handling.

The generally low rate of check rate when contrasted with different types of biometrics shows that the calculation utilized is not extremely strong and is defenseless against impacts like scaling and versatile disfigurements. Different new methods and calculation have been discovered which give better outcomes.

Likewise a noteworthy test in Fingerprint acknowledgment lies in the pre preparing of the terrible nature of unique mark pictures which additionally add to the low confirmation rate.

The target of this examination is to consolidate unique finger impression verification with the broadly utilized PIN validation conspire as of now utilized for online exchanges, to accomplish an idiot proof framework. An entire details extraction plot for programmed unique mark acknowledgment frameworks with canny strategy is exhibited. A basic stride is to dependably separate particulars from the unique mark pictures and process with fake neural system technique. Unique mark pictures are seldom of immaculate quality. They might be debased and defiled because of varieties in skin and impression conditions. Along these lines, unique finger impression details improvement strategies are utilized preceding particulars extraction to get a more solid estimation of details areas. In the main stage, picture standardization and introduction field of the unique mark are ascertained. The nearby introduction of the edges fills in as the parameter for the following handling stages. Particulars examples of the filtered and put away fingerprints are then thought about and assessment comes about are acquired by handling through managed counterfeit.

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